

RESEARCH AND MAINTENANCE STRATEGIES FOR LONG-TERM PRESERVATION RIGHTS OF OPEN ACCESS JOURNALS—A CASE STUDY OF THE NATIONAL SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY LIBRARY

Xin Li

*National Science Library,
Chinese Academy of Sciences
China*

*lix@mail.las.ac.cn
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2229-587X>*

Ziye Wang

*National Science Library,
Chinese Academy of Sciences
China*

*wangzy@mail.las.ac.cn
<https://orcid.org/0009-0001-2482-9978>*

Zhenxin Wu

*National Science Library,
Chinese Academy of Sciences
China*

*wuzx@mail.las.ac.cn
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4966-1961>*

This paper explores the legal foundations and implementation strategies for the long-term preservation of open access journals by libraries, using the National Science and Technology Library (NSTL) of China as a case study. Open access journals rely on the Creative Commons (CC) license system to provide a legal basis for replication, storage, and distribution in long-term preservation. Libraries can clarify preservation rights through long-term cooperation agreements with publishers, balancing technical, legal, and collaborative relationships. NSTL has established a hierarchical preservation strategy that integrates international collaboration and localized collection, building a long-term preservation system covering 13,000 journals. To date, NSTL has secured preservation agreements with publishers for 1,057 open access journals. Moving forward, NSTL will continue to strengthen digital preservation mechanisms in line with international standards, emphasizing the expansion of high-quality open access resource preservation within China.

I. OPEN ACCESS JOURNALS AND THE IMPORTANCE OF LONG-TERM PRESERVATION

1) Development of Open Access Journals

The concept of open access journals originated in the late 90s of the 20th century, when professionals in academia, library and information science began to realize the "academic journal crisis" in the traditional subscription publishing model. In this context, the concepts of open access publishing and open access journals were developed to provide an alternative model that could resist publishers raising the price of journals for high profits. Budapest Open Access Initiative (BOAI) is one of the landmark international initiatives that defines the concept of open access and emphasizes the freedom of users to access, use and share knowledge. Open access journals are an important part of the field of modern academic communication and publishing, and are an academic publishing model that follows the principles of open access, which allows authors to pay publication fees, such as review fees and editing fees, while readers can access the full text of peer-reviewed academic papers for free on the Internet. The emergence of this model is considered to be an important shift in the field of academic publishing, because it challenges the traditional subscription publishing model and provides a more convenient

and equal platform for scientific researchers and readers to communicate with each other. Since the concept of open access journals was proposed, it has gained momentum, and governments in many developed countries have begun to introduce policies to support and promote open access practices. For example, governments in the United States and the European Union require varying degrees of open access for projects supported by the government or taxpayers. This policy has led to a significant increase in the number and usage of open access journals. According to the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ), as of February 2025, nearly 21,367 peer-reviewed high-quality open access journals have been indexed.

2) The demand for Long-Term Preservation of Open Access Journals

The long-term preservation of open access journals helps keep knowledge open and accessible. In the era of information explosion, the speed of knowledge update is extremely fast, and as an important carrier of the academic community, the timely update and long-term preservation of the content of open access journals are essential for the dissemination and utilization of knowledge. Through the long-term preservation of open access journals, it can ensure that these valuable academic resources can be consulted and cited by subsequent researchers, regardless of the passage of time, so as to promote the depth of academic research and the advancement of knowledge.

Research shows that while all digital journals face the same threats, open access journals face unique challenges. Efforts around preservation and ongoing access are often aimed at ensuring access to subscription journals after cancellation, for which the library has already paid for. When journals are made available for free, the same financial incentives do not exist. In addition, unlike closed-access journals, which are typically funded by subscription, open-access journals rely on other funding sources, such as article processing fees (APCs) or sponsorships, to fund their publishing activities [1]. Journals that are particularly small and without APCs may have limited financial resources, and as a way to maintain operational costs, lightweight technology solutions such as university websites and servers or content management systems like WordPress may be opted for [2]. However, these options do not prevent technical instability and cannot ensure long-

term access to the journal's website if it cannot afford to participate in a preservation program [3]. The rate of participation of open access journals in preservation programs is alarmingly low, with 4 out of 10 journals indexed in DOAJ reporting at least one preservation or archiving program [4]. Due to the lack of a comprehensive and open archive, 174 open access journals disappeared from the web between 2000 and 2019, covering all major research disciplines and geographic regions of the world [5].

The long-term preservation of open access journals requires the joint efforts of all parties. Technical support, legal guarantees, and capital investment are all necessary conditions for the long-term preservation of open access journals. Therefore, support at the national level is needed, and the advantages of libraries and other institutions should be fully utilized to play their leading role in the long-term preservation of open access journals, and the long-term preservation of open access journals should be jointly promoted through multi-institutional and multi-level cooperation. JASPER (JournAIS are Preserved forever) is a digital long-term preservation initiative specifically designed for open access journals, launched by the DOAJ (Directory of Open Access Journals). Its aim is to ensure the permanent accessibility and integrity of open access journal content through technical collaboration and policy frameworks [6]. Led by the DOAJ, the program is jointly advanced by libraries, technical platforms, and academic institutions worldwide. Its core objectives include: permanently preserving open access journals to prevent content loss caused by journal discontinuation, platform shutdowns, or technological obsolescence; enhancing the sustainability of academic resources to support the open science movement and ensure long-term free access to research results; and reducing journal operation risks while providing low-cost preservation solutions for small or emerging open access journals. The preservation scope of JASPER covers all open access journals indexed in the DOAJ (currently exceeding 20,000 titles). Priority support is given to journals from low-income countries, independently published journals, or small journals with weak technical capabilities. Preserved content includes full-text journal articles (in formats such as PDF and XML), metadata, supplementary materials (e.g., datasets, code), and compatible preservation of dynamic content (e.g., interactive charts, enhanced papers). JASPER's

technical architecture adopts a distributed storage network, collaborating with established digital preservation organizations such as CLOCKSS and Portico to utilize their global nodes for redundant backup. Data storage adheres to the OAIS standard to ensure content traceability and recoverability. Journal content is automatically synchronized to the preservation platform via APIs or regular crawls, with only content following CC licenses (e.g., CC BY, CC BY-SA) being preserved. Attribution metadata is permanently bound to the content to meet open access protocol requirements. Key partners of JASPER include CLOCKSS, which provides decentralized archiving infrastructure; the Internet Archive, which supports content mirroring and format migration technologies; and library consortia (such as LIBER, the Association of European Research Libraries) that offer localized storage nodes and policy support. For a journal to join JASPER, it must first be indexed in the DOAJ (meeting open access transparency standards). Since JASPER services are currently free, a strict analysis of the journal's or publisher's financial status is conducted. If it is determined that the journal has obtained or is likely to obtain support or funding from organizations capable of covering long-term preservation costs, the right to exclude it is reserved. Subsequently, the journal must sign an archiving agreement authorizing content replication and long-term preservation, and complete technical integration through the OAI-PMH interface or manual upload. Readers access content through the original journal platform on a daily basis. If the original platform becomes unavailable, the archived content will be made accessible through CLOCKSS's trigger access mechanism or the Internet Archive's mirror repository.

II. COPYRIGHT LICENSE SYSTEMS FOR OPEN ACCESS JOURNALS: AUTHORIZATION AND CONSTRAINTS ON LONG-TERM PRESERVATION RIGHTS

1) *Rights Framework for Digital Preservation in Libraries*

In order to effectively protect the long-term preservation of the intellectual content purchased by the library, the library should have a reasonable right to archive, process and service the digital literature resources purchased or published openly. The right of archiving refers to the right of the library to ingest and archive the purchased data completely, timely and reliably, the right of processing refers to the right

of the library to inspect, convert, extract metadata, migrate and other processing of the archived data due to long-term preservation, and the right of service refers to the right of the library to use the preserved data to provide access services to authorized users under necessary conditions. In order to effectively implement these rights, libraries also have the right to eliminate the adverse effects of technological protection measures when exercising their preservation rights[8].

2) *The Framework of Copyright licenses system for Open Access Journals*

The copyright licensing system used in open access journals is largely based on Creative Commons (CC) licenses, which balance author rights with the accessibility of content [7]. A Creative Commons license, also known as a CC license, is a public copyright license that allows others to distribute a work. On December 16, 2002, Creative Commons, a non-profit organization in the United States, first released the CC license, with the purpose of allowing the work to be freely copied and disseminated under the premise that the author retains the relevant copyright rights, and to obtain and share more creations in the material without violating copyright protection laws. CC4.0 was released on November 25, 2013. Since then, CC 4.0 has been encouraged to be applied globally. In addition to relinquishing copyright to make a work fully public domain (i.e., CC0 License), there are a number of commonly used combinations of copyright provisions in CC 4.0. Such as: Attribution (CC-BY), Non-Commercial Use (CC-NC), Non-Derivative Works (CC-ND), ShareAlike (CC-SA). There are six different license types, listed from most to least permissive as follows:

CC-BY	enables reusers to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the material in any medium or format, so long as attribution is given to the creator. The license allows for commercial use.
CC BY-NC	enables reusers to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the material in any medium or format for noncommercial purposes only, and only so long as attribution is given to the creator

CC BY-NC-SA	enables reusers to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the material in any medium or format for noncommercial purposes only, and only so long as attribution is given to the creator. If you remix, adapt, or build upon the material, you must license the modified material under identical terms.
CC BY-ND	enables reusers to copy and distribute the material in any medium or format in unadapted form only, and only so long as attribution is given to the creator. The license allows for commercial use.
CC BY-NC-ND	enables reusers to copy and distribute the material in any medium or format in unadapted form only, for noncommercial purposes only, and only so long as attribution is given to the creator.
CC0	a public dedication tool, which enables creators to give up their copyright and put their works into the worldwide public domain. CC0 enables reusers to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the material in any medium or format, with no conditions.

Table1 *The Framework of Creative Commons (CC) licenses*

3) The scope of the CC licenses system allows for the core rights of digital long-term preservation

Digital long-term reproduction and storage rights, CC BY, CC BY-SA, CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND, and other licenses allow for unlimited copying and storage of content, including the creation of copies by institutions or third-party platforms for preservation purposes. CC0 (Public Domain) allows unlimited replication and archiving without any strings attached.

Format migration and conversion rights for digital long-term preservation often requires the conversion of content to a new format (e.g. PDF to XML). Format conversion is not explicitly prohibited in the CC license, but it is important to note that CC BY-ND (no derivations), which prohibits modification of content (including format conversion), may hinder the response to technical obsolescence. Other protocols allow format migration, as long as the original content integrity is preserved.

Distribution and access to digital long-term preservation, all CC licenses allow depositories to

distribute content to the public (unless the agreement contains NC restrictions).

4) Restrictions on the long-term preservation of digital data in the CC licenses system

While the CC license supports open access to intellectual content, certain provisions may pose implicit limitations on the long-term preservation of the digital. Ambiguity of Non-Commercial (NC) Terms. CC BY-NC prohibits use for "primary commercial purposes", but it is debatable whether long-term storage is a "commercial activity". For example, if the depository is operated by a commercial company (e.g., some cloud service providers), NC restrictions may be triggered. Whether a non-profit organization's use of a commercial technology platform is compliant or not needs to be judged in conjunction with judicial practice. Technical Impediments to Non-Derivative (ND) Clauses CC BY-ND prohibits modifications to the content, but long-term preservation often requires technical intervention (e.g., repairing corrupted files, migrating formats). Whether such operations are "derivative" is a matter of legal controversy and may limit the flexibility of depositories. Attribution (BY) requires long-term maintenance for all CC licenses. Depositories need to ensure that complete author and source information is retained for a long time, otherwise there may be a breach of the agreement. This places high demands on metadata management and technical systems.

5) The complementary role of legal and policy frameworks

Statutory Preservation Exceptions. Some national laws allow libraries and archives to reproduce works for preservation purposes (e.g., 17 U.S.C. §108 in the United States, Article 5 of the EU Copyright Directive). These exceptions may go beyond the limits of the CC license, subject to certain conditions (e.g., non-commercial, limits on the number of replicas in stock).

Institutional & Funder Policy. Funding agencies (e.g., NIH, Wellcome Trust) mandate that funded papers use the CC BY protocol and deposit them in designated knowledge bases (e.g., PubMed Central), which indirectly ensures long-term preservation rights.

Technology neutrality. Some legal interpretations hold that technical modifications (e.g., format migration) do not constitute "deduction", thus

allowing preservation operations under the CC BY-ND license, but need to be supported by judicial precedents.

The system of copyright agreements for open access journals provides the basis for long-term digital preservation, but non-commercial (NC) and non-derivative (ND) clauses can pose practical obstacles. Legal exceptions and institutional policies can partially compensate for contractual limitations, depending on the specific judicial environment. In the future, a more sustainable digital preservation ecosystem can be built through protocol optimization, technical tools, and legal collaboration.

III. THE ROLES AND RIGHTS OF LIBRARIES IN LONG-TERM PRESERVATION OF OPEN ACCESS JOURNALS

1) *The impact of long-term preservation for digital resources on libraries*

The impact of the rise of open access journals on libraries is manifold, especially in the area of long-term preservation. With the proliferation of digital resources, libraries need to select and preserve them for a long time to ensure their usability and credibility. The long-term preservation of open access resources requires not only that libraries have the right technical equipment and expertise to handle this data, but also that intellectual property issues need to be taken into account. Libraries must ensure that they do not infringe copyright when preserving open access resources, and they also need to establish good relationships with the providers of the resources.

Libraries also play a role in education and training in the long-term preservation of open access journals. Libraries need to educate users about the concept of open access, educate them on how to access and use these resources, and how to share and preserve them safely. This not only helps to increase users' awareness of open access resources, but also enhances their research and learning capabilities.

The long-term preservation of open access journals presents new challenges and opportunities for libraries. Libraries need to constantly update their technologies and services to adapt to this trend, and they also need to actively explore opportunities to collaborate with open access journal publishers to jointly promote the development and use of open access resources. Through these efforts, libraries are

not only better able to serve their users, but also maintain their central position in the digital age.

2) *Analysis of Libraries' Interests in the Long-Term Preservation of Open Access Journals*

The rights and interests that are inevitably involved in the long-term preservation of open access journals are different from those of commercial subscription electronic journals. For example, the long-term preservation of resource ingestion rights in open access journals is difficult to obtain through the constraints of procurement contracts, etc. However, according to the definition of open access and the provisions of the CC license, the reproduction of open access resources is a reasonable reuse. Therefore, the localized preservation of open journal content by libraries usually does not involve equity risks. However, open access resources do not necessarily automatically guarantee trustworthy long-term preservation, and there are still rights management requirements and limitations on harvesting open access resources. Even if the open resource hosting system allows the search and download of open content, it is still necessary to examine the copyright regulations of the content owner or the host system, so as not to affect the normal operation of the host system, and respect its first service right. It is necessary to carefully read and understand the rights statement of the host system, for example, NIH emphasizes that the copyright of the Author Accepted Manuscripts stored in it belongs to the author, and the institution that searches and downloads it must respect these rights; PubMed Central considers its OAI and FTP interfaces as the only channels for downloading services and prohibits any other automated download activities. In addition, it is important to have authoritative metadata of the preserved content and reliable audit information of the overwritten resources, which require the cooperation of the publisher.

A reasonable way to ensure long-term collaboration between libraries and publishers for the long-term preservation of open access journals is to use acquisition agreements or open publishing cooperation agreements to request collaboration. These agreements are tools for libraries to tie their investments in ordering or supporting open publishing to their service requirements. The main rights and interests of the library for the long-term preservation of open access journals include: (1)

allowing the widest possible range of access rights and reuse rights, such as the CC-BY license for open published content; (2) provide free, high-quality, and reliable search services; Provide services for automatically depositing papers published by the institution (in a specific format) into the institutional repository; (3) to provide services that regularly and reliably store relevant content in a specific format in a local preservation system; (4) support open interoperability; (5) Support related extension services, reuse, open links and text mining.

IV. PROGRESS OF LOCALIZED PRESERVATION STRATEGIES AND PRACTICES OF THE NATIONAL SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY LIBRARY IN THE LONG-TERM PRESERVATION OF OPEN ACCESS JOURNALS

1) *Localized Preservation Strategies*

The National Science and Technology Library (NSTL), as an important scientific and technological literature information resource guarantee and service organization in China [9], has carried out a series of practices in the local preservation of open access journals in recent years, mainly adopting the strategy of establishing a hierarchical and step-by-step mechanism, including safeguard strategies and long-term preservation strategies. The so-called national security strategy refers to the fact that it does not have the right to preserve, but can obtain the full text and carry out centralized management, so as to achieve the goal of centralized custody of data assets, and then become a part of the national resource security system; The long-term preservation strategy refers to the establishment of a reliable long-term preservation service that follows international rules and conforms to international standards and norms to ensure the integrity and correctness of the preserved digital scientific and technological literature resources. The specific methods are: first, the systematic evaluation and selection of open access resources and the cooperative collection of localization, and the second is the cooperation of the long-term preservation rights and interests agreement of the localization of open access resources.

2) *Implementation Progress*

Systematic evaluation and selection of NSTL open access resources and localized collaborative collection. Through international cooperation and independent collection, NSTL systematically collects important open access journal resources around the

world, covering natural sciences, engineering technology, medicine and other fields, with a special focus on the resource integration of high-impact journals and preprint platforms. Through the selection, collection, processing, organization and disclosure of open resources, the resources of different platforms and different literature types are integrated and integrated, and an open access resource integration system is constructed, which is used to open the public to retrieve foreign open access resource abstracts and provide browsing jump services. At present, the NSTL open access integrated system contains various open access resources, and has revealed more than 13,000 foreign open access journals, more than 8,700 open access conference papers, more than 8,000 open access scientific and technological reports, 90,000 open access dissertations, more than 64,000 open access courseware, and about 100,000 open access books [10].

The Long-term Preservation Center of NSTL conducts rights and interests cooperation agreements with publishers to obtain long-term preservation authorization. In 2013, the National Digital Preservation Program (NDPP) was led by the National Science and Technology Library and Documentation Center (NSTL), and the relevant institutions in the United Nations systematically and comprehensively implemented the localization of digital scientific and technological literature resources, especially the localized long-term and reliable preservation of externally sourced digital scientific and technological literature resources. Various potential dangers such as geopolitics lead to problems such as the inability to reliably use digital resources in China for a long time, providing a strategic guarantee for national scientific and technological information security. In May 2023, the National Digital Preservation Center (NDPC) was officially inaugurated [11]. Established by the Library and Information Center of the Chinese Academy of Sciences, NDPC undertakes the work related to the long-term preservation of NSTL digital science and technology literature resources, and comprehensively promotes the construction of a long-term preservation system for China's digital science and technology literature resources. The NDPC has set up six preservation nodes for long-term preservation, namely the Library and Information Center of the Chinese Academy of Sciences (hereinafter referred to as the "Chinese

Academy of Sciences Node"), the Institute of Scientific and Technical Information of China (hereinafter referred to as the "CITIC Node"), the Peking University Library (hereinafter referred to as the "Peking University Node"), the Institute of Agricultural Information of the Chinese Academy of Agricultural Sciences, and the Institute of Medical Information/Library of the Chinese Academy of Medical Sciences, China Books Import & Export (Group) Co., Ltd. NDPC is positioned as a national long-term preservation center in China, and the preservation strategy is to safely preserve important core digital science and technology literature resources, expand the security preservation of new digital science and technology literature resources, give priority to the preservation of digital science and technology literature resources that are in line with its own strategic positioning, large usage, high academic value, high risk, and strong preservation operability, and have reached cooperation agreements with 56 resource suppliers for 87 resource (database) authorization to localize long-term preservation in Chinese main land. It contains 13,000 journals and 147,000 e-books, and has built the largest long-term preservation resource content system covering high-quality digital science and technology literature at home and abroad.

As open access publishing has become the mainstream trend of academic resource publishing in recent years, NDPC has paid more attention to and promoted the long-term preservation rights and interests cooperation of open access journals. In order to achieve cooperation on the long-term preservation rights and interests of important open access journal resources, NDPC has formulated a long-term preservation agreement applicable to open access resources, clarifying the rights and obligations of long-term preservation institutions when acquiring, preserving and providing open access resources, and ensuring legal compliance Clarity of regulation and responsibility. NDPC has established a unified format and standard, standardize the technical process and quality control of long-term preservation institutions in the processing of OA resources, and ensure technical feasibility and quality reliability. NDPC has also established the selection criteria for long-term storage of OA resources, and give priority to the preservation of higher-quality OA resources according to the amount of system storage and

resource selection priority, so as to ensure cost controllability and improve storage efficiency.

The agreement on the long-term preservation rights and interests of open access journals adopted by the NDPC is basically based on the framework of the terms and conditions of the long-term preservation cooperation of subscribing to digital journal resources. In terms of triggering events, access initiation and termination, guarantee and liability, storage data format, storage data transmission frequency, etc., it maintains a unified mechanism for long-term preservation rights and interests of subscribed digital resources. On the one hand, the NDPC relies on various preservation centers and sub-centers to include its fully open access journals in the scope of long-term preservation rights and interests on the basis of negotiating with traditional commercial publishing houses for long-term preservation rights and interests of subscribing to digital resources. On the other hand, NDPC's preservation centers and sub-centers are negotiating open access publishing cooperation plans with fully open access publishers, and the long-term preservation rights and interests of open access publishing cooperative journals are included in the overall cooperation agreement. To date, NDPC has entered into long-term preservation rights partnerships for a total of 1,057 fully open access journals with three publishers, including one traditional commercial publisher, Wiley, and two fully open access publishers, BMC and PenSoft.

Figure 1 Statistics on the quantity of preserved open access journal titles of NDPC

The plan for the long-term preservation of open access resources of the NDPC in the future. At present, NDPC is formulating a conservation resource plan for the next 3-5 years, and will carry out a conservation plan to rapidly increase the scale and coverage of high-quality resource preservation resources, and continue to strengthen the long-term preservation of high-quality open access resources in China will be an important area of cooperation. The NDPC will discuss and negotiate long-term preservation agreements for open access resources with key publishers and fully open publishers on open access resources, such as Elsevier, Frontiers, MDPI, PLOS, J-stage, etc., follow international digital long-term preservation norms and industry standards, standardize the operation mechanism of digital long-term preservation management, give full play to the role of China's national document resource guarantee platform, and jointly promote the long-term preservation and development of digital documents.

V. CONCLUSION

The long-term preservation of open access journals is essential to ensure the sustainability of academic resources and global knowledge sharing, but some open access journals are at risk of disappearing due to technical or economic issues. Open access journals use the CC protocol system to provide a legal basis for long-term preservation for reproduction, storage and distribution. Libraries need to balance technical, legal, and partnerships, with clear preservation interests (e.g., content access, format conversion, metadata management) through acquisition agreements or open publishing partnerships. The practice of localized preservation of open access resources carried out by the national long-term preservation center for digital science and technology literature resources built by the National Science and Technology Library and Documentation Center of China shows that the cooperation agreement on hierarchical preservation strategy, localized collection and storage and long-term preservation rights and interests can effectively integrate global high-quality open access resources, build a localized preservation system, and set the goal of continuously expanding the scale of open access resource preservation in the next 3-5 years.

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AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

Xin Li: Deputy Director of the Data Resources Department and Associate Research Librarian at the National Science Library of Chinese Academy of Sciences. Main professional focus areas include scientific literature resource development, with continuous tracking and research on open access development, as well as long-term preservation rights of digital resources procured by libraries.

Ziye Wang: Librarian from the National Science Library of Chinese Academy of Sciences, participating in the negotiations for long-term preservation rights of resources under NDPC.

Zhenxin Wu: Research Librarian at the National Science Library of Chinese Academy of Sciences and Deputy Director of NDPC, responsible for the technical systems of NDPC's long-term preservation.

